

Strategies to control the growth of unwanted microalgae during the production of *Arthrospira platensis* BEA 005B using exhausted culture media

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ABSTRACT

When producing *Arthrospira platensis* (Spirulina) it is essential to reuse the exhausted culture medium for sustainability reasons. However, this strategy is challenging given the negative effect the medium has on microalgal growth. While recycling helps reduce costs and environmental impact, it can also result in an increased risk of biological contamination. Indeed, in this study, harvesting *Arthrospira platensis* using a 100 µm mesh led to an accumulation of an unwanted microalga identified as *Chlorella* sp. To address this issue, various strategies were evaluated. These included the use of sea salt, increasing the pH, heating the culture, or adding an additional ultrafiltration step. The results showed that the most effective solution was to incorporate a 0.2 µm membrane filter. This technique eliminated the *Chlorella* sp. cells from the culture medium, resulting in a 15% increase in the *A. platensis* biomass production compared to unfiltered cultures. Adjusting the pH of the culture to 10.5 also limited the growth of *Chlorella* sp. without significantly affecting *A. platensis* growth. This strategy proved suitable for delaying the accumulation of *Chlorella* sp. but did not avoid its appearance. The findings reported in this work underscore the importance of choosing appropriate separation methods to ensure the purity and productivity of *A. platensis* cultures in large-scale production systems.

Keywords: Spirulina, sustainability, water management, filtration, biomass.

1. Introduction

Commercial interest in Spirulina has increased significantly over recent decades. It is now the most widely produced and consumed microalga in the world [1]. Spirulina is the trade name for *Arthrospira platensis* and *Arthrospira maxima*. Its primary use is as a food source, predominantly being sold as a dietary supplement. However, it is also used in various products as a protein source, a natural colourant, or as part of a marketing strategy. Numerous Spirulina-enriched foods have been developed and examined in scientific research [2]. Most studies indicate that even at concentrations of 1-5%, Spirulina can significantly enhance the nutritional and bioactive properties of foods.

Spirulina can be produced economically in large open photobioreactors. Raceway ponds (or raceways) are considered the most cost-effective option. Its extremophilic optimum pH range of 9-12 significantly lowers the risk of contamination. While centrifugation is the conventional method for harvesting the microalgal biomass, Spirulina's larger size simplifies the process. Harvesting using a filter or a mesh with pores larger than 50 μm is cheaper than centrifugation and allows one to achieve an efficiency of around 95% [3]. Regardless of the separation method, reusing the supernatant is vital for reducing production costs and improving sustainability. Moreover, recycling the nutrient-depleted medium for microalgae cultivation significantly reduces the environmental impact by lowering resource demand and waste generation [4]. Water management strategies such as medium recycling help reduce the environmental impact of microalgae production, saving up to 75% of the water and nutrients [5]. Nevertheless, recycling poses challenges such as contamination, which can impair microalgal growth [6]. As mentioned above, Spirulina is an extremophilic microalga that thrives at high pH, making it less susceptible to

contamination. However, Spirulina can still become easily contaminated, for example, by insects [7]. Spirulina cultures can also become contaminated with other microorganisms, including microalgae, especially when produced using open outdoor ponds. This can cause significant problems for large-scale production. This issue is particularly prevalent when the cultivation medium is recirculated, as contaminants might accumulate over time. Biological contamination by other microalgae, such as *Chlorella* spp., is a key concern for large-scale *Arthrospira platensis* cultivation, since it affects both productivity and biomass quality. Despite reports since the early 1980s of *Chlorella* spp. or other strains occasionally appearing in *Arthrospira* cultures, limited research has been focused on this issue to date. For instance, *Chlorella* contamination can be prevented by maintaining a high bicarbonate concentration (0.2 M) and raising the culture temperature [8], although the cost of these strategies is high. Other studies evaluated the potential use of microfiltration as a pre-treatment step before returning the exhausted medium back into the reactor. However, the cost of heating the culture or adding a microfiltration stage is not viable for some producers.

The goal of this study was to identify novel strategies to avoid the growth of unwanted microalgae in cultures of *Arthrospira platensis* BEA 005B, appearing mainly when the exhausted medium is recirculated. Different strategies were investigated including filtration, the addition of sodium chloride, and adjusting the pH or temperature. These different strategies were validated over three consecutive production runs. This is the first time that contamination control strategies for this microalga have been reported. Moreover, this study demonstrates two different strategies that can control the growth of unwanted microalgae. The effectiveness of these strategies varied as did the cost of applying them, thus offering solutions to both large and small-scale Spirulina producers.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Background information

An 80 m² raceway reactor at the University of Almeria (Spain) was used to produce *A. platensis* BEA 005B. The reactor was operated in semi-continuous mode (0.2 day⁻¹). For the biomass production, a culture medium composed of the following commercial fertilizers was used: 0.9 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.14 g·L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 0.18 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄·7H₂O, 8.4 g·L⁻¹ NaHCO₃ and 30 mg·L⁻¹ of Karentol[®] (Kenogard, Barcelona, Spain), a commercial mixture of agricultural micronutrients [9]. Harvesting was carried out using a 100 μm membrane. The exhausted culture medium (the permeate) was recirculated back into the system. Nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations in the exhausted medium were measured and adjusted daily to match the concentration levels described above. Spectrophotometric methods, detailed elsewhere, were used for the nitrogen and phosphorus determinations [10]. After 20 days of semi-continuous production, microscopic observations revealed that an unwanted microalga was growing and accumulating in the system. The unwanted strain was identified as a *Chlorella* sp. by Sanger sequencing using the BigDye Terminator v3.1 kit on an Applied Biosystems ABI3500 genetic analyser (Waltham, Massachusetts, USA).

The harvested biomass, which contained mainly *A. platensis* cells but also the unwanted *Chlorella* sp., was then resuspended in fresh culture medium up to a final biomass concentration of 1.0 g·L⁻¹. This culture was used as the inoculum for the activities described below.

2.2. Photobioreactors used

Biomass production was conducted using 300 mL bubble columns, as described elsewhere [11]. The culture was exposed to 12 h of light and 12 h of darkness; the

maximum irradiance inside the columns without cells was $1,850 \mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, measured using an SQS-100 spherical quantum sensor (Walz GmbH, Effeltrich, Germany). The temperature and the pH were maintained constant at $25.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 9.5 , respectively.

2.3. Medium reuse

The contaminated *A. platensis* culture obtained from the 80 m^2 raceway reactors was used to inoculate the bubble columns. The initial biomass concentration was $0.2\text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The culture medium's composition was identical to that described above. Harvesting was carried out using a $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ membrane. The filtered medium was used to produce biomass at four different recirculation percentages: 0 (control), 33, 66, and 100%. As part of the water was retained with the biomass, the recirculation percentage of 100% refers to the recirculation of all the recovered water, but it represented approximately 90% of the inlet medium. The nutrient content of the exhausted medium was analysed as described elsewhere [10] and was supplemented with fertilisers to match the initial concentrations. Three independent photobioreactors were used per treatment, each one being the experimental unit.

2.4. Contamination control

The unwanted *Chlorella* sp. strain was isolated and grown in the same culture medium described in the previous section. The effects of four treatments on the growth of this strain were evaluated: i) increasing the pH to 10.5 using 0.5 N sodium hydroxide; ii) adding sodium chloride up to a concentration of $5.0\text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$; iii) keeping the temperature controlled at $40.7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and iv) adding an extra filtration stage using a $0.2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ membrane. The biomass production was performed in the same photobioreactors described in the previous sections. The effect of these treatments on *A. platensis* was also investigated. The biomass production was carried out in triplicate using three independent photobioreactors.

2.5. Analytical determinations

The daily measurements included assessing the optical density at 680 and 750 nm using a GENESYS 10S UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Spain). The chlorophyll fluorescence parameter, Fv/Fm, was determined using an AquaPen AP 100 fluorometer (Photo System Instruments, The Czech Republic) as described before [12]. Each determination was conducted in triplicate. At the beginning and end of each batch production cycle, the biomass concentration was determined by dry weight, as described before [12]. The biomass productivity was calculated using the equation:

$$\text{Biomass productivity (g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}) = \frac{C_f - C_0}{t}$$

where C_f and C_0 are the final and initial biomass concentration and t is the duration of the production stage.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Statistical differences were analysed using ANOVA with Statgraphics (Statgraphics Technologies, Inc. The Plains, VA, USA) while Fisher's LSD test was applied to differentiate between the means. A significance threshold of $p < 0.05$ was used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of culture medium reuse on cell growth

As explained above, *A. platensis* was produced in an 80 m² raceway reactor using recirculated culture medium obtained using a 100 µm membrane. During this process, an unwanted microalga identified as *Chlorella* sp. appeared and then accumulated in the culture. Recirculation of exhausted culture medium can also promote the appearance and growth of other contaminants such as bacteria or algal predators. In

this study, no rotifers or algal predators were identified in the raceways. The appearance and growth of unwanted strains represents a challenge. For example, in a previous study aimed at producing *Tetraselmis chuii* for feeding eastern oysters, the culture became contaminated on various occasions with a cyanobacterium, *Synechococcus* sp., which took over the culture within days [16]. The microalga identified as *Chlorella* sp. appears in cultures of *A. platensis* in summer (in Almeria), especially when reusing the exhausted culture medium after harvesting using a 100 μm membrane.

Figure 1A shows the effect of reusing the culture medium at different recirculation percentages on the biomass concentration of *A. platensis*. Overall, in the second production cycle it seemed that the reutilization of exhausted medium stimulated the growth of the microalga. However, in the third production cycle it was clear that medium reutilization negatively affected growth. In the culture with no recirculation, the maximum biomass concentration achieved was 1.43 ± 0.05 , while this value was 1.22 ± 0.01 , 1.15 ± 0.02 and $0.96 \pm 0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in the cultures produced using 33, 66 and 100% of reused medium, respectively ($p < 0.05$). This represents a reduction in the biomass concentration of 14.7, 19.6 and 32.9%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). There are some studies available in the literature on the effect of culture medium reutilization and the results vary significantly. For example, the use of exhausted medium replenished with nutrients decreased the culture productivity of *Nannochloropsis* sp. by 50% compared to the control [17]. Similarly, in another study, a 50% reduction in the cellular yield was observed after 4 batch cycles of recirculation [18]. Conversely, no significant effect on the growth of *Chlorella vulgaris* was noted after two months of reusing exhausted medium, with the productivity remaining stable at approximately $0.55 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ [19]. Similar results have been observed for *Spirulina*. For example,

a daily reutilisation of 75% of the exhausted medium for 2 weeks did not affect the biomass productivity or the biomass protein content [20]. Repeatedly recycling the *A. platensis* culture medium led to a decline in both the growth rate and the Fv/Fm value compared to a control culture produced using fresh medium [21]. In the present work, the biomass concentration achieved was lower than that reported in other studies. For example, previous studies achieved a maximum concentration of 1.9 g·L⁻¹ [22] and 2.61 g·L⁻¹ [23]. This could be caused by using different strains and culture media, or by the contaminant that negatively affected the *A. platensis* growth still being present. Biological contaminants can reduce growth rates and biomass productivities [24]. *Chlorella* strains usually have a high growth rate and compete with other strains for nutrients. In this study, the growth rate of the *Chlorella* cells was not higher than that of *A. platensis* (shown below) but it still reduced nutrient availability. The higher cell density of cells not harvested using the 100 µm membrane also reduced light availability in the subsequent production cycle. This did not represent a challenge in the bubble columns, where light availability is high, but it might limit growth in raceway reactors.

Photosynthetic organisms are very sensitive to stress [25]. Fv/Fm can be used as an indicator of the status of the culture. For example, in a previous study, recycling the *Arthrospira platensis* culture medium four times resulted in a 2-fold decrease in Fv/Fm compared to non-recirculated medium [26]. Green algae and cyanobacteria have significantly different quantum yield values, with green algae showing optimal values at around 0.6-0.7 and cyanobacteria at around 0.4-0.5. The lower values observed in cyanobacteria are primarily due to the interfering fluorescence emitted by the light-harvesting antennae of the phycobilisomes [27]. The Fv/Fm values observed (Figure 1B), especially at the highest production cycles and recirculation percentages

($p < 0.05$), are closer to those of eukaryotic microalgae than to those of prokaryotic cyanobacteria. This suggests that the culture contained and increased abundance of eukaryotic microalgae. Microscopic observations (Figure 2) demonstrated that the strain that was accumulating in the raceways was also taking over the indoor culture. Because of its small size, this unwanted microalga passed through the 100 μm membrane (together with small fragments of *Spirulina*) and accumulated in the system. Overall, the higher the recirculation rate, the greater the presence of this unwanted microalga. The main reason for its accumulation was because the exhausted medium was being reutilised and the growth rate of both strains was comparable, as described in the following section. The photorespirometric determinations (data not shown) revealed an identical oxygen production rate under the study conditions.

3.2. Strategies to reduce the growth of *Chlorella* sp.

3.2.1. Incorporating an additional filtration step

Given that the *Chlorella* sp. strains passed through the 100 μm membrane and accumulated in the system (Figure 2), the first strategy was to include an additional filtration step using a 0.2 μm membrane. The results (Figure 3A) indicated that the concentration remained constant over all the production cycles. This demonstrated that the reutilization of the culture medium was successful, with no *Chlorella* cells present in the medium and no negative effects on the biomass concentration. Microscopic observations (Figure 3B) showed that filtering with both 100 μm and 0.2 μm membranes successfully removed short filaments of *Spirulina* as well as *Chlorella* cells from the culture medium. Recycling the medium without prior treatment can lead to the accumulation of algae, protozoan grazers, cell debris, and residual bacteria.

Therefore, culture medium recycling requires treating the supernatant before replenishing and reusing it [28]. Filtration is already used to control other biological contaminants in microalgae cultures, such as adult rotifers, which are larger than 200 μm [29]. In this study, the incorporation of an additional filtration step demonstrated its potential for minimising the proliferation of unwanted small microalgae.

The implementation of additional filtration steps might not be possible for small producers since it requires extra labour and the purchase and installation of new equipment. Contamination can occur rapidly, quickly overtaking *Spirulina* cultures. Therefore, implementing an immediate control strategy is crucial. Chemical control methods and modifying the culture conditions (e.g., light, temperature, or pH) might be good strategies to manage competitive microalgae contaminating *Spirulina* cultures. These strategies might also improve the growth rate of the target algae while negatively affecting the growth rate or reducing the presence of undesirable contaminants [30].

3.2.2. Increasing the pH from 9.5 to 10.5

The pH is a crucial factor for microalgae as it affects the solubility/availability of nutrients, including CO_2 . Cultivating microalgae under alkaline pH conditions can also enhance CO_2 mass transfer, leading to a high concentration of HCO_3^- ions that promote rapid *Spirulina* growth [31]. The growth of unwanted strains or microorganisms can be limited by controlling the alkalinity of the medium [32].

The effect of pH on microalgae is strain dependent. For example, a previous study found that the maximum productivity for *Chlorella sorokiniana* occurred at pH 6, with biomass productivity decreasing as the pH increased from 6 to 9 [33]. This is in line with other study that concluded that *Chlorella vulgaris* preferred to use CO_2 under acidic conditions rather than HCO_3^- under alkaline conditions [34]. *Spirulina* can thrive

in both freshwater (pH 7) and alkaline environments (pH 9-11), particularly in tropical and subtropical regions [35]. The optimal pH for *A. platensis* was calculated as 9, with the lowest growth observed at pH 11 [31]. The ability of *A. platensis* to adapt to high pH levels is remarkable and quite unique [36]. A previous study determined that *Arthrospira platensis* BEA 1257B could grow well up to a pH of 10.5, indicating a significant alkaliphilic adaptation in the strain [37].

Figure 4A shows the effect of modifying the pH of the culture to 10.5 using sodium hydroxide. Overall, the productivity of *A. platensis* was not affected, while the productivity of *Chlorella* was significantly reduced ($p < 0.05$). The increased pH led to a 73.5% reduction in unwanted *Chlorella* strain productivity compared to the control at pH 9.5 ($p < 0.05$). Although *Chlorella* was still able to grow under these conditions, its growth was much slower ($p < 0.05$). This did not happen with *A. platensis*. Therefore, the strategy was selected for potential further development. This phenomenon could be explained by the fact that, at pH values greater than 10, CO_2 is no longer present, leaving HCO_3^- as the only usable form of inorganic carbon [38]. The effectiveness of using HCO_3^- varies among species. Some species rely on HCO_3^- to supplement CO_2 as a carbon source, while others can fully meet their carbon needs with HCO_3^- alone: HCO_3^- is the most favoured inorganic carbon source utilised by *Spirulina* [39]. After testing the strategy of raising the pH to 10.5 separately in both cultures, it was further validated in a culture where both strains were present together and where the culture medium was recirculated using a 100 μm membrane. The pH of the culture was adjusted to 10.5. The data presented in Figure 4B show that the biomass concentration was stable throughout all the production cycles. This stability was observed regardless of the recirculation percentage applied, except for the final production run where the non-recirculated medium resulted in a slightly higher

biomass concentration compared to the other treatments ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that while the strategy may delay *Chlorella* accumulation, it might not be effective for very long recirculation periods, as *Chlorella* cells were still present in the culture.

3.2.3. Other physical and chemical approaches

Temperature is recognized as a crucial factor in the growth of microorganisms. *A. platensis* thrives in lakes with average temperatures around 25 ± 10 °C but also in shallow lakes where the temperature can reach 40 °C during the warmer seasons. The optimal temperature for cultivating *Spirulina* in the lab is typically around 35 °C, but this can vary among different species. Some strains grow between 38 and 40 °C, while others grow better in the 28-36 °C range [40]. In a previous study, *A. platensis* C1 was able to grow at 42 °C using urea as a nitrogen source [41]. The authors of that work observed just a 6.6% reduction in growth compared to the control at 35 °C. Not all microalgae can cope with high temperatures. For this reason, applying high temperatures could be an effective strategy to control contamination while allowing the growth of *A. platensis*. *Chlorella* species are also known for their ability to thrive across a wide range of temperatures although these are generally milder. Figure 5A shows the effect of increasing the culture temperature to 40 °C for 12 h per day on both cultures (*A. platensis* and *Chlorella* sp.). This temperature was selected based on preliminary photorespirometric determinations of *Arthrospira platensis* BEA 005B (data not shown). The batch test lasted 9 days. However, on the seventh day, the *A. platensis* culture crashed while the *Chlorella* sp. proved to be more tolerant managing to grow despite the high temperature. In the case of *Chlorella* sp., the biomass productivity was reduced by 50% compared to the control ($p < 0.05$). Overall, the use of temperature was not an efficient solution for controlling the growth of the unwanted *Chlorella* strain. Although some *Spirulina* strains can cope with high temperatures,

others are less resistant. For example, the optimum cultivation temperature for *A. platensis* was 35°C, at which the highest growth rate was observed (0.29 day⁻¹), while the lowest growth rate (0.21 day⁻¹) was recorded at 40 °C [42]. It was also reported that the dry weight of *A. platensis* C1 incubated at 42 °C for 24 h was 32% lower than the control cultivated at the optimal temperature of 35 °C [43]. The reason for this could be that heat stress reduces PSII activity and disrupts electron transport on the acceptor side of PSII in *A. platensis* [44]. In addition, there are some species of *Chlorella* that can grow at high temperatures. For example, *Chlorella sorokiniana* LWG002615 was isolated from a culture at a temperature of 44 °C [45]. The temperature a culture can tolerate and use to maximize productivity depends on the duration of exposure.

Arthrospira sp. has not yet been found living naturally in marine environments [46] but it is known that it can adapt to a variety of aquatic environments including wastewater and seawater. In previous studies, an acclimated *A. platensis* was able to cope with the highest salinities tested (60 g·L⁻¹ NaCl), growing similarly to the control, which was produced in Zarrouk medium [47]. In contrast, a different study found that, as the NaCl concentration increased, the growth of *Chlorella* decreased [48]. When NaCl concentrations exceeded 30 g·L⁻¹, *Chlorella* could not tolerate it, resulting in no algal growth. In another study, in which *Chlorella protothecoides* was cultivated under heterotrophic conditions for lipid production, the microalga was gradually inhibited as the NaCl concentration increased, ceasing entirely above 30 g·L⁻¹ due to apparent toxicity [49]. Since salinity seems to affect *Chlorella* strains more than it affects *Arthrospira*, NaCl addition was evaluated as a potential strategy for controlling contaminant growth. Figure 5B shows the biomass productivity of *A. platensis* and *Chlorella* sp. cultures after adding 5 g·L⁻¹ NaCl. The concentration was selected

because of previous experience with this microalga, which demonstrated that it was able to adapt to increased salt concentrations of $5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Greater increases without an adaptation stage led to lower productivities (data not shown). Overall, *A. platensis* showed an 81.5% decrease in productivity ($p < 0.05$) while *Chlorella* productivity remained almost unaffected. Also, the time it took to achieve the maximum biomass concentration with salt was 7 days compared to 11 days in the medium without salt. This may be due to an increased growth rate induced by salt stress. Therefore, increasing salinity does not appear to be an effective tool for contamination delay in *A. platensis* cultures. The negative effect of salt on *A. platensis* growth could be attributed to the absence of an acclimatization period for the organism. The length of the acclimatization period seems to significantly affect tolerance levels, as evidenced by the observation that acclimating *A. platensis* in seawater for several generations reduces the negative impact of salinity on growth. [47,50]. Earlier studies demonstrated that *A. platensis* exposed to shorter acclimation periods suffered negative effects even at low salinities ($< 10 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$). However, strains adapted to a salinity of $15 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ showed the same growth as the control after three generations [51]. Although most *Chlorella* strains cannot grow beyond $30 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of salt, some can thrive with salinity. For example, a salt concentration ranging from 5 and $20 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ enhanced the maximum biomass concentration of *Chlorella vulgaris* compared to the culture without salt [52]. Additionally, the biomass productivity of *Chlorella vulgaris* YH703 increased 1.3-fold in media with $1.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ NaCl compared to the control [53]. Similarly, it has been shown that the biomass yield of *C. vulgaris* increased with the addition of $5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ NaCl to the medium [54]. This effect may be due to salinity providing sodium ions that are crucial for photosynthesis in microalgae, as they help regulate intracellular pH, absorb inorganic nutrients, and tolerate alkalinity [55].

4. Conclusions

This study assessed the impact of reusing exhausted culture medium on the production of *A. platensis* and explored strategies for controlling the growth of an unwanted extremophile *Chlorella* strain. The results revealed that reusing the culture medium, recovered after filtration using a 100 µm membrane, negatively affected the productivity of *A. platensis*. Higher recirculation percentages led to increased accumulation of the unwanted *Chlorella* strain, mainly because it accumulated in the culture due to its small size (<100 µm). Two effective strategies for controlling this contamination were identified. The first consisted of adding a 0.2 µm filtration step before reusing the exhausted medium, which successfully removed the *Chlorella* while maintaining *A. platensis* levels. The second consisted of raising the pH to 10.5, which reduced *Chlorella* productivity significantly without impacting *A. platensis*. Increasing the pH might be an easier option for small-scale Spirulina producers as no extra equipment is required. However, while adjusting the pH delayed *Chlorella* accumulation, this strategy might not be effective for very long recirculation periods, as *Chlorella* cells were still present in the medium. Increasing the temperature to 40 °C or adding NaCl were not effective in controlling the growth of *Chlorella*, either because they did not negatively affect the *Chlorella* growth or that they did negatively affect *A. platensis*.

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CRedit Contributor Roles

S. Villaró: Investigation, Formal analysis, Supervision, and Writing – Original draft; **S. Valero-Cardoso:** Investigation; **C. Cerdá-Moreno:** Investigation and Formal analysis; **M. Ciardi:** Investigation; **T. Lafarga:** Writing – Review & editing, Supervision and Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The research data will be provided by the corresponding author at reasonable request.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Effect of culture medium reuse on (A) the biomass concentration and (B) the Fv/Fm ratio. Values represent the mean value of three independent determinations. The medium was collected using a 100 µm membrane. Different lowercase letters indicate statistical differences between production cycles and different uppercase letters indicate significant differences between the percentage of medium reused ($p<0.05$).

Figure 2. Micrographs of (A) 0% medium reuse, (B) 33% medium reuse, (C) 66% medium reuse and (D) 100% medium reuse.

Figure 3. (A) Effect of culture medium reuse on the biomass concentration. Values represent the mean value of three independent determinations. The medium was collected using a 100 µm membrane followed by filtration using a 1 µm membrane. (B) Micrograph of the filtered culture medium: (i) 100 µm and (ii) 100 followed by 1 µm.

Figure 4. Effect of pH increase from 9.5 to 10.5 on (A) the growth of the isolated strains and (B) contamination control during culture medium reutilization. The medium was collected using a 100 µm membrane. Different letters denote statistically significant differences ($p<0.05$).

Figure 5. Effect of (A) NaCl addition and (B) temperature control on the growth of *A. platensis* and *Chlorella* sp. Different letters denote statistically significant differences ($p<0.05$).

Figure 1

(A)

(B)

Figure 2

Figure 3

(A)

(B)

Figure 4

Figure 5

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